

Rongchengshi 容成氏

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** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Chinese Religion, Early Chinese text, Excavated text, Text

The Rongchengshi 容成氏 is a bamboo text of fifty-three strips, making it one of the longest Chu-script manuscripts yet discovered. Unfortunately, some of the strips are damaged and at least one strip is missing from both the beginning and end of the manuscript. While it has some parallels with the received tradition, the text has no exact counterpart and was thus previously unknown to scholars before its discovery. It was part of a collection of such texts purchased by the Shanghai Museum in three batches in Hong Kong in 1993. The texts were looted from a tomb by grave robbers and their exact provenance is thus unknown. Similarities with the collection of texts excavated near the village of Guodian 郭店 in Hubei province in 1993, suggest that the Shanghai texts may have come from Guojiagang 郭家崗 Tomb One near the village of Guodian, though there is no way to confirm this. The Shanghai texts likely date from around the same period as the Guodian texts (between 300 BCE to 278) and the text of the Rongchengshi itself was likely written at the end of the 4th century BCE, a point indicated by its resemblance to ideas of the late 4th and early 3rd centuries. The text is a work of political philosophy that articulates its argument through an historical narrative that stretches from high antiquity to the beginning of the Zhou 周 dynasty. It is the only pre-Han 漢 dynasty work to offer such a narrative. Moreover, it is also unique among pre-Han works in attributing the practice of abdication to rulers of high antiquity. Other unusual features of the text include the fact that it advocates a utopian vision in which all people are employed according to their abilities and that it presents a devolutionary reading of history in which society gradually declines from high antiquity through subsequent ages. The goal of the text is to advocate for a political system that will follow the features described above and in which a meritorious ruler will use lenient and frugal rule to achieve harmony with heaven and earth. The latter point is particularly important as it indicates a shift away from a prioritization of the mandate of Heaven (the idea that Heaven sanctions the ruling lineage) to a prioritization of harmony with heaven and earth. Because of its devolutionary scheme, however, the text does not advocate abdication but suggests that, within the benighted conditions of the contemporary age of the Warring States, rulers should achieve power by garnering the allegiance of the common people. A final important feature of the text is the unusual list of sages that it presents in its opening strips (the text's title is based on the fact that the first of its listed sage-rulers is named Rongchengshi). While the text's list has some parallels with other works, it is not an exact match. The names of many of the sages in the text's sequence, along with other features of the work, suggest that it may be more representative of the regional culture of the state Chu 楚 than the common elite culture that Chu shared with the other states of the North China plains.

Date Range: 325 BCE - 278 BCE

Region: Shanghai Museum

Region tags: China

The Shanghai Museum (Shanghai Bowuguan 上海博物馆) purchased a cache of bamboo texts (the "Shanghai Strips") in Hong Kong. Because these texts are looted materials, their provenance is unknown. As many of them are previously unknown texts, the only

known location that can be associated with them is the museum itself.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Allan, Sarah. *Buried Ideas: Legends of Abdication and Ideal Government in Early Chinese Bamboo-Slip Manuscripts* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 2015).
- Source 2: Shanghai Bowuguan cang Zhanguo Chu zhushu 上海博物館藏戰國楚竹書. Edited by Ma Chengyuan 馬承源 (Shanghai: Shangjai Guji, 2001), vol. 2, 91-146; 247-293.

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– Yes

↳ Cemetery
– Field doesn't know

↳ Temple
– Field doesn't know

↳ Shrine
– Field doesn't know

↳ Altar
– Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional marker
– Field doesn't know

|

- ↳ Cenotaph
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Church
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mosque
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Synagogue
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Monument
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Hilltops
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

↳ Specify

–Specify: The Rongchengshi was part of a collection of bamboo texts that were purchased by the Shanghai Museum in three batches in Hong Kong in 1994. These texts were originally stored in a tomb, but because they were sold by tomb robbers who had looted them, their provenance is unknown and no information is available regarding the site. Based on newspaper reports of tomb robberies as well as similarities with the corpus of texts discovered at Guodian 郭店 Tomb One, it is possible that this collection came from Guojiagang 郭家崗 Tomb One near the village of Guodian 郭店. There is, however, no certainty regarding this speculation (Allan 2015, 51-58). Presently, it is stored in the Shanghai Museum along with the rest of the Shanghai collection.

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

Notes: The Rongchengshi is an unusually long excavated text written on fifty-three bamboo strips, though not all are completely intact.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: Bamboo stalks would have been cut into sections and then into strips, upon which the text was written. The strips were bound before being tied with cords.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Unknown

Notes: No information is available on this point.

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The uncertain provenance of the text means that no information is available regarding issues of production or intended audience.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the lack of information regarding the text, is impossible to answer this question with any certainty. The text itself is work of political theory articulated using an historical narrative. It is unknown how much authority was invested in it by its authors and readers.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text is written in Classical Chinese and would, presumably, have been accessible to any literate person of the time.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the text was buried in a tomb, it can be considered part of the ritual practice of formal burial, although the details of its role are not known. Most likely, the text was a personal possession of the deceased that was placed in the tomb in order to reflect the identity of the deceased as perceived by his or her mourners (Allan 2015, 26; 57-58)

Is there material significance to the text?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: As mentioned above, King Wu states that Heaven (the supreme thearch) intends to punish King

Zhou for his tyranny. While this would seem to suggest some form of supernatural monitoring, the text does not provide further details (Allan 2015, 217).

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above. The text is written as a continuous historical narrative.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text's historical narrative is divided into different time periods stretching from high antiquity to the beginning of the Zhou. The chief concern of that history is the ruling lineages and the methods by which they ruled. The overall framework is a devolutionary one in which each historical age is considered inferior to the one that preceded it.

Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The lineages in question are exclusively those of the ruling elite and so they possess the highest authority of each age.

Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

Notes: Different methods of establishing and continuing the ruling lineage are specific to different historical time periods (such as high antiquity).

How is the lineage established?

– Other [specify]: Abdication

Notes: The text explains that in highest antiquity, the time of greatest harmony, kings regularly

abdicated the throne in order to pass it on at the end of their reigns to worthy individuals. This practice continued in the time of Yao, Shun, and Yu (discussed in following notes), but broke down with the establishment of the Xia, Shang, and Zhou dynasties.

—Other [specify]: The allegiance of people throughout the world.

Notes: Yao, the first of the three sovereigns following high antiquity, gained power by garnering the allegiance of the world through caring and frugal government. He then abdicated the throne to Shun who, in turn, abdicated it to Yu. However, this system broke down when Yu's son, Qi, usurped the throne from Yi (to whom Yu had attempted to abdicate the throne) and established hereditary rule, beginning the three dynasties (though the text does not name them as such). Qi's descendants formed the Xia dynasty, which was eventually overthrown by Tang. Tang gained power in the same manner as Yao, but continued the practice of hereditary rule, as did Wu, the founder of the Zhou dynasty.

—Other [specify]: As discussed above, certain rulers, such as Qi, Tang, and Wen, established new governments either through usurpation or winning of the allegiance of the world, but then initiated periods of hereditary rule in which the ruling lineage was defined by patrilineal descent (known in other texts as the time of the Three Dynasties).

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

— No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

— No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

— No

Notes: Because of the devolutionary framework with which the text articulates its history, it suggests that different modes of establishing one's rule (such as attracting loyalty vs. abdication) are appropriate to different eras (Allan 2015, 183-184). That being said, the text does emphasize the importance of cosmic harmony and caring for the people across different contexts.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

— No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

— Yes

Notes: Heaven is described as intending to punish King Zhou (Allan 2015, 217).

Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

— Yes

Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: It is stated that Heaven intends to punish King Zhou because of his misrule, tyranny, and lack of concern for his subjects (Allan 2015, 216-217).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The text provides few details about the nature of Heaven's punishment of King Zhou, other than the fact that it will bring his rule to an end. Because King Wu resolves to attack Zhou in support of Heaven's punishment, it thus includes defeat in battle.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: Thus far, only one manuscript of the Rongchengshi has been discovered and the work is unknown in the received tradition.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Assuming that all of the texts in the Shanghai collection came from the same tomb, they presumably reflect the personal library of the deceased and were placed in the tomb in order to reflect the deceased's identity as the mourners understood it (Allan 2015, 26; 56-57). As a result, there is no sense of canonization in the collection.

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: When the sage-kings reign well it is stated that the sky and earth support them. However, this seems to be the result of their ability to harmonize the cosmos as opposed to direct reward by supernatural forces (Allan 2015, 192-194; 203).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The "worthiness" of an individual is considered the most important criterion for becoming king.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Notes: Both King Tang and King Wu are said to have defeated wicked kings (Jie and Zhou respectively) in battle, though their personal courage is not explicitly mentioned (Allan 2015, 252; 258).

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Notes: Courage is not mentioned explicitly, but can be seen as an implicit element of the sage-kings' willingness to endure hardships in order to care for the people.

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: The sage-kings are all distinguished by their broad-minded care of, and concern for, the common people.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: Sage-king Yao is said to have been lenient and to not employ harsh punishments (Allan 2015, 232).

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: Sage-kings of highest antiquity were said to garner few taxes (Allan 2015, 228).

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: The sage-kings of highest antiquity are said to have abdicated the throne to those of worth without prioritizing their own families (Allan 2015, 190-191).

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: The "worthiness" of an individual is considered the most important criterion for becoming king.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Only in the sense that sage-kings properly follow correct rituals, not in the sense of abstaining from sources of impurity (Allan 2015, 236).

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: When sage-king Yao visits Shun to consider giving him the throne, the two sages treat one another with respect and courtesy (Allan 2015, 236).

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: The filial piety of sage-king Shun is said to have positively transformed his kin (Allan 2015, 236).

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Both Tang and Wen remain loyal to wicked rulers (Jie and Zhou respectively) because it is their duty (Allan 2015, 252; 256). Eventually the depravity of these rulers forces those loyal to overthrow them.

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: The sagely mode of ruler is frequently described in collaborative terms. For example, Yu is said to have "followed the desires of the people" (Allan 2015, 245).

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: Many of the most important features of human civilization, including music, agriculture, waterworks, and law, are said to be the creations of sages.

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Notes: Moderation and frugality characterize the reigns of the sage-kings and are key aspects of their ability to harmonize with the cosmos. Sage-king Yu is singled out by the text for the austerity of his lifestyle (Allan 2015, 247).

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: Sage-king Yu is said to have personally dug trenches and other waterworks to control flooding (Allan 2015, 240). Similarly, Hou Ji endures deprivation in the wilds in order to bring

agriculture to the common people (Allan 2015, 242). Both Tang is praised for this forbearance in serving under the wicked king Jie until he achieves the allegiance of the people (Allan 2015, 252).

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: The diligence of the sage-kings is implied in all descriptions of their ruling and caring for the common people. Yu, for instance, is said to have heard the complaints of his subjects no matter the weather (Allan 2015, 247).

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: Many sages, e.g. Yu, only accept the throne after they fail in their efforts to find someone worthier to take it in their place (Allan 2015, 244).

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: When describing King Wen, the text states that "he thoroughly understood the benefits of high and low, fertile and barren (terrain). He knew the way of heaven and the benefits of the earth, and kept the people from being troubled" (Allan 2015, 256). The understanding of other sages (with respect to the nature of the cosmos, music, the law, etc.) are also emphasized.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: This is an implicit feature of the sages and their ability to both rule and innovate.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: The sage-kings of highest antiquity are described as employing all people according to their specific traits so that everyone is given a place for within society and cared for (Allan 2015, 190-191). Harmonizing with the cosmos is also an essential aspect of sagely rule.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The text articulates a political philosophy using the "only known narrative history composed before the Han dynasty that stretches from high antiquity to the beginning of the Zhou." The text is thus an argumentative work that would have been read as such by its audience. It advances a vision of ideal government in which all people are employed according to their abilities and harmony with heaven and earth is prioritized and the heavenly mandate disregarded as a source of authority (Allan 181-182).

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The only mention of a burial in the text is when the work states that, after his death, the sage-king Yu's tomb did not "muddy the springs below it." This was because the tomb itself was shallow. In making this statement, the text is not concerned with the burial itself, but rather in using it as an example of Yu's austerity and humility in both life and death (Allan 2015, 207-211).

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: Yu's tomb is not specified save for the fact that it was very shallow (a sign of austerity).

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: The burial of Yu is explicitly described as simple and thus not intensive.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: When King Wen (the posthumous founder of the Zhou dynasty) is described as serving Zhou, the tyrant-king of the Shang, he is said to have worn an undyed robe, as if he were in mourning. Similarly, his son, King Wu, is described as wearing an undyed head-covering (also indicative of mourning) when setting out with his army to vanquish King Zhou (Allan 2015, 214-217).

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The reference is very minor. Generally, the text refers to the "sky (tian) and earth" as a way of referring to the cosmos as a whole. However, in one instance, King Wu refers to the fact that Heaven (tian) will punish Zhou, the tyrant-king of the Shang. In this instance, the term "heaven" is used as a euphemism for the supreme thearch (Shangdi), the high god of the Shang and Zhou (Allan 2015, 217). Because of the limited nature of this reference, the questions below can only be answered as "I don't know," because the text itself provides so few details and it is unclear if its conception of Heaven would have matched the portrayals of other Warring States' texts.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: The term "di" 帝 suggests that he was an ancestor and so, in some sense, human.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– I don't know

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– I don't know

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– I don't know

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– I don't know

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward

– I don't know

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: King Wu states that Heaven intends to punish Zhou for his tyrannical ways (Allan 2015, 216).

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: King Wu claims that his military attack on King Zhou is meant to assist Heaven's punishment by "overawing" Zhou, thus making Heaven the ostensible cause of his actions (Allan 2015, 216-217).

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– I don't know

Notes: Heaven/the supreme thearch is not described as exhibiting any emotion in the text, despite the fact that King Wu states that it will punish King Zhou (Allan 2015, 216).

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– I don't know

↳ Can be hurt?

– I don't know

↳ Can be tricked?

– I don't know

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: None

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– I don't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?
– No

Previously human spirits are present
– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?
– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?
– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?
– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?
– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?
– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: However, given that the text is an argumentative work, it is presumably meant to convince its readers to adopt what it advocates.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Non-human animals and plants

Notes: When describing the harmonious reigns of past sage-kings, the text repeatedly mentions their effect on non-human worlds. For example, the rule of sage-king Shun was said to cause both plants and the "birds and beasts" to flourish (Allan 2015, 203). More notably, during the earlier reign of Youyu Tong, "birds and beasts arrived at court and fish and turtles presented (themselves)" (Allan 2015, 192-193).

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: Thus far, only one manuscript of the Rongchengshi has been discovered and the work is unknown in the received tradition.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Assuming that all of the texts in the Shanghai collection came from the same tomb, they presumably reflect the personal library of the deceased and were placed in the tomb in order to reflect the deceased's identity as the mourners understood it (Allan 2015, 26; 56-57). As a result, there is no sense of canonization in the collection.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The text articulates a political philosophy using the "only known narrative history composed before the Han dynasty that stretches from high antiquity to the beginning of the Zhou." The text is thus an argumentative work that would have been read as such by its audience. It advances a vision of ideal government in which all people are employed according to their abilities and harmony with heaven and earth is prioritized and the heavenly mandate disregarded as a source of authority (Allan 181-182).

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: None of the above. The text is written as a continuous historical narrative.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text's historical narrative is divided into different time periods stretching from high antiquity to the beginning of the Zhou. The chief concern of that history is the ruling lineages and the methods by which they ruled. The overall framework is a devolutionary one in which each historical age is considered inferior to the one that preceded it.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The lineages in question are exclusively those of the ruling elite and so they possess the highest authority of each age.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

Notes: Different methods of establishing and continuing the ruling lineage are specific to different historical time periods (such as high antiquity).

↳ How is the lineage established?

–Other [specify]: Abdication

Notes: The text explains that in highest antiquity, the time of greatest harmony, kings regularly abdicated the throne in order to pass it on at the end of their reigns to worthy individuals. This practice continued in the time of Yao, Shun, and Yu (discussed in following notes), but broke down with the establishment of the Xia, Shang, and Zhou dynasties.

–Other [specify]: The allegiance of people throughout the world.

Notes: Yao, the first of the three sovereigns following high antiquity, gained power by garnering the allegiance of the world through caring and frugal government. He then abdicated the throne to Shun who, in turn, abdicated it to Yu. However, this system broke down when Yu's son, Qi, usurped the throne from Yi (to whom Yu had attempted to abdicate the throne) and established hereditary rule, beginning the three dynasties (though the text does not name them as such). Qi's descendants formed the Xia dynasty, which was eventually overthrown by Tang. Tang gained power in the same manner as Yao, but continued the practice of hereditary rule, as did Wu, the founder of the Zhou dynasty.

–Other [specify]: As discussed above, certain rulers, such as Qi, Tang, and Wen, established new governments either through usurpation or winning of the allegiance of the world, but then initiated periods of hereditary rule in which the ruling lineage was defined by patrilineal descent (known in other texts as the time of the Three Dynasties).

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The only mention of a burial in the text is when the work states that, after his death, the sage-king Yu's tomb did not "muddy the springs below it." This was because the tomb itself was shallow. In making this statement, the text is not concerned with the burial itself, but rather in using it as an example of Yu's austerity and humility in both life and death (Allan 2015, 207-211).

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: Yu's tomb is not specified save for the fact that it was very shallow (a sign of austerity).

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: The burial of Yu is explicitly described as simple and thus not intensive.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: When King Wen (the posthumous founder of the Zhou dynasty) is described as serving Zhou, the tyrant-king of the Shang, he is said to have worn an undyed robe, as if he were in mourning. Similarly, his son, King Wu, is described as wearing an undyed head-covering (also indicative of mourning) when setting out with his army to vanquish King Zhou (Allan 2015, 214-217).

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The reference is very minor. Generally, the text refers to the "sky (tian) and earth" as a way of referring to the cosmos as a whole. However, in one instance, King Wu refers to the fact that Heaven (tian) will punish Zhou, the tyrant-king of the Shang. In this instance, the term "heaven" is used as a euphemism for the supreme thearch (Shangdi), the high god of the Shang and Zhou (Allan 2015, 217). Because of the limited nature of this reference, the questions below can only be answered as "I don't know," because the text itself provides so few details and it is unclear if its conception of Heaven would have matched the portrayals of other Warring States' texts.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: The term "di" 帝 suggests that he was an ancestor and so, in some sense, human.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - I don't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - I don't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can reward
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
 - Notes: King Wu states that Heaven intends to punish Zhou for his tyrannical ways (Allan 2015, 216).
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

Notes: King Wu claims that his military attack on King Zhou is meant to assist Heaven's punishment by "overawing" Zhou, thus making Heaven the ostensible cause of his actions (Allan 2015, 216-217).

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– I don't know

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– I don't know

Notes: Heaven/the supreme thearch is not described as exhibiting any emotion in the text, despite the fact that King Wu states that it will punish King Zhou (Allan 2015, 216).

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– I don't know

↳ Can be hurt?
– I don't know

↳ Can be tricked?
– I don't know

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
–Specify: None

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– I don't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

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Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

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Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: As mentioned above, King Wu states that Heaven (the supreme deity) intends to punish King Zhou for his tyranny. While this would seem to suggest some form of supernatural monitoring, the text does not provide further details (Allan 2015, 217).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Heaven is described as intending to punish King Zhou (Allan 2015, 217).

Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: It is stated that Heaven intends to punish King Zhou because of his misrule, tyranny, and lack of concern for his subjects (Allan 2015, 216-217).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The text provides few details about the nature of Heaven's punishment of King Zhou, other than the fact that it will bring his rule to an end. Because King Wu resolves to attack Zhou in support of Heaven's punishment, it thus includes defeat in battle.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: When the sage-kings reign well it is stated that the sky and earth support them. However, this seems to be the result of their ability to harmonize the cosmos as opposed to direct reward by supernatural forces (Allan 2015, 192-194; 203).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: Because of the devolutionary framework with which the text articulates its history, it suggests that different modes of establishing one's rule (such as attracting loyalty vs. abdication) are appropriate to different eras (Allan 2015, 183-184). That being said, the text does emphasize the importance of cosmic harmony and caring for the people across different contexts.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The "worthiness" of an individual is considered the most important criterion for becoming king.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Notes: Both King Tang and King Wu are said to have defeated wicked kings (Jie and Zhou respectively) in battle, though their personal courage is not explicitly mentioned (Allan 2015, 252; 258).

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Notes: Courage is not mentioned explicitly, but can be seen as an implicit element of the sage-kings' willingness to endure hardships in order to care for the people.

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: The sage-kings are all distinguished by their broad-minded care of, and concern for, the common people.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: Sage-king Yao is said to have been lenient and to not employ harsh punishments (Allan 2015, 232).

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: Sage-kings of highest antiquity were said to garner few taxes (Allan 2015, 228).

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: The sage-kings of highest antiquity are said to have abdicated the throne to those of worth without prioritizing their own families (Allan 2015, 190-191).

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: The "worthiness" of an individual is considered the most important criterion for becoming king.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Only in the sense that sage-kings properly follow correct rituals, not in the sense of abstaining from sources of impurity (Allan 2015, 236).

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: When sage-king Yao visits Shun to consider giving him the throne, the two sages treat one another with respect and courtesy (Allan 2015, 236).

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: The filial piety of sage-king Shun is said to have positively transformed his kin (Allan 2015, 236).

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Both Tang and Wen remain loyal to wicked rulers (Jie and Zhou respectively) because it is their duty (Allan 2015, 252; 256). Eventually the depravity of these rulers forces those loyal to overthrow them.

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: The sagely mode of ruler is frequently described in collaborative terms. For example, Yu is said to have "followed the desires of the people" (Allan 2015, 245).

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: Many of the most important features of human civilization, including music, agriculture, waterworks, and law, are said to be the creations of sages.

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Notes: Moderation and frugality characterize the reigns of the sage-kings and are key aspects of their ability to harmonize with the cosmos. Sage-king Yu is singled out by the text for the austerity of his lifestyle (Allan 2015, 247).

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: Sage-king Yu is said to have personally dug trenches and other waterworks to control flooding (Allan 2015, 240). Similarly, Hou Ji endures deprivation in the wilds in order to bring agriculture to the common people (Allan 2015, 242). Both Tang is praised for this forbearance in serving under the wicked king Jie until he achieves the allegiance of the people (Allan 2015, 252).

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: The diligence of the sage-kings is implied in all descriptions of their ruling and caring for the common people. Yu, for instance, is said to have heard the complaints of his subjects no matter the weather (Allan 2015, 247).

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: Many sages, e.g. Yu, only accept the throne after they fail in their efforts to find someone worthier to take it in their place (Allan 2015, 244).

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: When describing King Wen, the text states that "he thoroughly understood the benefits of high and low, fertile and barren (terrain). He knew the way of heaven and the benefits of the earth, and kept the people from being troubled" (Allan 2015, 256). The understanding of other sages (with respect to the nature of the cosmos, music, the law, etc.) are also emphasized.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: This is an implicit feature of the sages and their ability to both rule and innovate.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: The sage-kings of highest antiquity are described as employing all people according to their specific traits so that everyone is given a place for within society and cared for (Allan 2015, 190-191). Harmonizing with the cosmos is also an essential aspect of sagely rule.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: However, given that the text is an argumentative work, it is presumably meant to convince its readers to adopt what it advocates.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: The text does, however, emphasize the orderliness and efficiency of sagely governments.

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text frequently mentions how kings (both bad and good) subdued, or attempted to subdue, others by military means. For example, both King Tang and King Wu are said to have defeated wicked kings (Jie and Zhou respectively) in battle (Allan 2015, 252; 258).

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: The text dates from the Warring States period (475-221 BCE), a time after the Zhou dynasty when multiple, centralizing states engaged in constant warfare with one another (Allan 2015, 11-15).

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: It does, however, emphasize that lenient (or no) taxes are a form of sagely rule and that the establishment of taxes in passes and markets created anger and resentment among the common people (Allan 2015, 25).

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: However, all major features of human civilization ranging from music to law to agriculture are said to be the creations of sage-kings and their sage ministers (Allan 2015, 242).

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: In addition to mentioning that sages in highest antiquity provided food to all people, the text describes how Hou Ji invented agriculture (Allan 2015, 225, 242)

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: In general, the text does not specify welfare institutions, but it describes sagely ages as ones in

which all people are employed according to their ability and cared for. Accordingly, the rule of a sage would obviate the problems meant to be addressed by welfare institutions.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Unknown

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Unknown

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: In addition to defining sagely ages as ones in which all people are cared for and employed according to their abilities, the text makes special mention of the fact that, in highest antiquity, the "disabled and rejected were not discarded. Whoever was left in obscurity, the (rulers taught and instructed. They gave them drink and food" (Allan 2015, 225).

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: While it is generally thought that women were excluded from education during the Warring States, there is some evidence that women may have been educated and literate (though not necessarily due to official sanction) (Allan 2015, 55-58).

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

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Does the text specify forms of taxation?

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